

UPWARDS

Deliverable D5.2

Parameter identification tool for intra-laminar fatigue damage modelling of unidirectional GFRP laminates

WP	5	Material failure models
Task	5.2	Intra-laminar progressive damage model for fatigue loading and inverse parameter identification tool

Dissemination level ¹	PU	Due delivery date	31.03.2020
Nature ²	R	Actual delivery date	04.05.2020

Lead beneficiary	SINTEF AS
Contributing beneficiaries	SAMTECH SA

Document Version	Date	Author	Comments ³
1	2020.04.16	Nicolas Krumenacker (SINTEF), Cédric Lequesne (SAMCEF), Hu Xiong (SAMCEF)	Creation
2, Final	2020.04.27	Nicolas Krumenacker (SINTEF), Cédric Lequesne (SAMCEF), Hu Xiong (SAMCEF)	

¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU), **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

² Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report, **P** = Prototype, **D** = Demonstrator, **O** = Other

³ Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

Deliverable abstract

Lightweight composite structures have an important role to play in meeting the sustainable energy goals of tomorrow. The implementation of the modelling state-of-the-art in commercial applications is a key activity to improve the performance and design life of these structures. To this end, a semi-empirical framework is implemented in the Simcenter Samcef commercial finite element code using the intralaminar fatigue damage model and the cycle-jump algorithm that were developed by van Paepegem. An additional parameter identification tool is developed to reverse engineer the material-specific parameters of the model based on data from four-point flexural experiments. A sequence of five specific layups are tested using a laminated GFRP material used in wind turbine blades, which consists of non-crimp fabric plies. The model is validated by comparing simulated and experimental results using digital image correlation for a sixth layup that is selected to be more representative of structures in service.

The implemented modelling framework was able to correctly identify the parameters that govern the stiffness degradation observed during the first two stages of a typical fatigue curve. However, the parameters governing failure in stage III were not correctly identified given that the selected material failed with a significant interlaminar shear component, which the van Paepegem model was not designed to handle. A new coupon design free of stitching could be instrumental in supplying intralaminar failure data for future combined inter- and intralaminar modelling approaches.

Deliverable Review

Reviewer #1 / Coordinator: Jens Kjær Jørgensen			Reviewer #2: Brian LV Bak, AAU		
Answer	Comments	Type*	Answer	Comments	Type*

1. Is the deliverable in accordance with

(i) The Description of Work?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(ii) The international State of the Art?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Not applicable for this deliverable	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Not applicable for this deliverable	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a

2. Is the quality of the deliverable in a status

(i) That allows it to be sent to European Commission?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(ii) That needs improvement of the writing by the originator of the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(iii) That needs further work by the Partners responsible for the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a

* Type of comments: M = Major comment; m = minor comment; a = advice.

Table of content

1. Introduction	4
1.1. Background	4
1.1.1. Definition of the damage variables	5
1.1.2. Fatigue behaviour law	6
1.1.3. Fatigue failure indices	7
1.1.4. Laws for the evolution of fatigue damage in a unidirectional ply	7
1.1.5. Plastic strain accumulation	8
1.2. Objectives	8
2. Methodology	9
2.1. Mechanical testing	9
2.1.1. Test configuration and setup	9
2.1.2. Materials and coupon preparation	10
2.1.3. Quasi-static testing method	11
2.1.4. Fatigue testing method	12
2.2. Intra-laminar fatigue modelling	14
2.2.1. Finite element model implementation	14
2.2.2. Model parameter identification tool	15
2.3. Model validation method	16
3. Results and discussion	19
3.1. Mechanical testing results	19
3.1.1. Quasi-static testing	19
3.1.2. Fatigue testing	22
3.2. Inverse parameter identification	24
3.2.1. FE model implementation.	24
3.2.2. Results of the parameter identification tool	26
3.3. Model validation	32
4. Conclusion	34
Reference	35

1. Introduction

The European Union has set out an aspiring Goal No. 7 to "ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all" as part of its renewed 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development [1]. One activity that will aid in meeting this vision is the development and industrial proliferation of state-of-the-art modelling tools for lightweight composite materials. The latter play an important role in the development of key economic sectors such as aerospace and renewable energy production in the form of load-bearing structures such as lighter-weight integrated airframes [2] and wind turbine blades [3], respectively.

Still, failure prediction in laminated composites remains far from mature. Multiple failure modes can act at different scales and often interact, most notably in the case of more complex structures and load cases. Predicting the fatigue life of composite structures is especially important as they experience a wide range of dynamic loading conditions over their life spans with varying amplitude and frequency, e.g. low amplitude vibrations arising from atmospheric and rotor wake turbulence [4]. As a composite laminate ages under cyclic load, its stiffness degrades and its deflection augments including permanent (or plastic) deformation. For a wide range of continuous fibre-reinforced polymers (FRP), the degradation is owed to the onset and evolution of intralaminar damage, i.e. within laminated plies, in the form of matrix microcracking [5]. These microcracks eventually connect as they grow and result in fibre failures and the formation of transverse ply cracks. Failure finally occurs once the load-bearing plies become sufficiently compromised and interply delamination cracks form. This report sets out to implement a state-of-the-art modelling tool within an industrial framework to predict the fatigue life of glass fibre-reinforced polymer (GFRP) laminates and capture the aforementioned stiffness degradation.

1.1. Background

Sevenois and van Paepegem [6] reviewed the state-of-the-art of fatigue modelling methods for FRP, and more specifically compared the different approaches for modelling unidirectional (UD) and 2-D woven reinforcement architectures. In doing so, they determined that semi-empirical residual stiffness models based on experimental data are suitable to predict fatigue performance and can be subsequently combined with residual strength models.

The semi-empirical modelling approach utilized in this report is based on the stiffness degradation laws developed by van Paepegem and Degrieck [7], including tensile and compressive damage coupling [8], as well as the cycle-jump (or N-Jump) approach developed by van Paepegem *et al.* [9], which was implemented in a finite element (FE) code. The cycle-jump algorithm effectively skips or "jumps" over the simulation of fatigue loading cycles that negligibly contribute to the stiffness degradation history. The damage state is instead updated at cycle increments over which a significant albeit controlled increase in stiffness degradation occurs. The aim is to minimize computational run costs and times while preserving good fidelity with the experimental data being fed to the finite element model (FEM). These methods are fully described by van Paepegem in [10].

The overarching aim of this fatigue damage model is to predict the different stages of the stiffness degradation curve for a wide range of FRP materials. Fig. 1. Illustrates the typical fatigue curve for a wide range of FRP materials (adapted from [7]). Stage I corresponds to a rapid albeit small initial drop in stiffness, which is dominated by the onset of transverse matrix cracking and progresses non-linearly with the number of cycles. In turn, stage II corresponds to a prolonged albeit small drop in stiffness, which progresses approximately linearly with respect to the number of cycles. The damage manifested during this stage is mainly the growth of longitudinal matrix cracks along 0° fibres and small delamination cracks at the coupon edges. Lastly, stage III corresponds to a transition from matrix damage to fibre damage and a precipitous non-linear final drop in stiffness, which accounts for the bulk of the laminate stiffness.

The work carried out by van Paepegem and Degrieck was intended for 2D woven reinforcement architectures. Carrella-Payan [11] extended their modelling approach to capture the fatigue behaviour of UD plies. The underlying fatigue behaviour law is described for a UD ply in the following theory sections.

Fig. 1. Typical fatigue curves for a wide range of FRP materials (adapted from [1]).

1.1.1. Definition of the damage variables

Three damage variables are defined to capture the different types of intralaminar damage: longitudinal (i.e. along to the fibre direction), D_{11} ; transverse (i.e. in-plane normal to the fibre direction), D_{22} ; and in-plane shear, D_{12} . These damage variables directly affect the lamina stiffness response. The 1-2-3 Cartesian axes correspond to the fibre, transverse, and through-thickness ply orientations, respectively, i.e. the on-axis reference frame. First, they are assembled into the diagonal damage stiffness matrix:

$$\text{diag}(\underline{\underline{D}}) = \langle D_{11} \quad D_{22} \quad 0 \quad D_{12} \quad 0 \quad 0 \rangle \quad (1)$$

Damage is either caused by static or fatigue loading. These two types of damage types are combined into a single damage matrix:

$$\underline{\underline{D}} = \underline{\underline{D}}^s + \underline{\underline{D}}^f \quad (2)$$

where $\underline{\underline{D}}_s$ and $\underline{\underline{D}}_f$ represent the static and fatigue damage components, respectively. However, the fatigue behaviour law used herein does not capture the onset and evolution of static damage. An initial value can instead be considered:

$$\underline{\underline{D}} = \underline{\underline{D}}^f, \text{ where: } \underline{\underline{D}}(t = 0) = \underline{\underline{D}}^s \quad (3)$$

Each damage term is a unit ratio between 0 and 1 with a value of 0 signifying an undamaged material and a value of 1 signifying complete failure. In practice, the failure value is limited set very close to but not exactly 1 to avoid numerical issues, i.e. a singular stiffness matrix:

$$D_{ij} = \min(D_{ij}, d_{\max}), \text{ where: } d_{\max} \leq 0.999 \quad (4)$$

The effect of fatigue damage on the lamina stiffness differs between tensile and compressive loading state. Crack closure can occur during the latter. The fatigue damage tensor is computed as follows. The function $\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle$ filters positive values of σ_{ij} , which is used to compute the effect of the damage state on the stress tensor over the current time step.

$$D_{ij}^f = D_{ij}^{f+} \frac{\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle}{|\sigma_{ij}|} + D_{ij}^{f-} \frac{\langle -\sigma_{ij} \rangle}{|\sigma_{ij}|} \quad (5)$$

$$\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle = \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_{ij} + |\sigma_{ij}|) \quad (6)$$

Instances of the fatigue damage matrix, \underline{D}^{f+} and \underline{D}^{f-} , represent the fatigue damage due to tensile and compressive loading states, respectively. They are computed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{ij}^{f+} &= d_{ij}^+ + d_{ij}^- \\ D_{ij}^{f-} &= h d_{ij}^+ + d_{ij}^- + (1 - h) \delta_{i4} \delta_{4j} d_{12}^+ \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where h is a material coefficient that differentiates the impact of the damage in case of tensile or compressive stress and characterizes the crack closure effect. It can be fixed at a value of $h = 0.2$ according to [10]. In turn, the components d_{ij}^+ and d_{ij}^- correspond of the damage due to tensile and compressive state. Fig. 2 illustrates the difference in fatigue damage evolution over a single cycle between damage components depending on whether the corresponding stress is positive or negative. It is a simplified case meant to illustrate the reasoning for separating the tensile and compressive damage states given the different damage modes. It should be noted that no such difference exists in the case of in-plane shear.

Fig. 2. Interpretation of the tension-compression fatigue loading cycle.

1.1.2. Fatigue behaviour law

The fatigue behaviour law is formulated as follows:

$$\underline{\sigma} = \underline{C} \underline{\varepsilon}^e = \underline{H} \underline{S}^{-1} \underline{H} (\underline{\varepsilon} - \underline{\varepsilon}^p) \quad (8)$$

where \underline{S} and \underline{H} are the stiffness and on-to-off axis transformation matrices, respectively:

$$\underline{S} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1^0} & -\frac{\nu_{12}^0}{E_1^0} & -\frac{\nu_{13}^0}{E_1^0} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}^0}{E_1^0} & \frac{1}{E_2^0} & -\frac{\nu_{23}^0}{E_2^0} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{13}^0}{E_1^0} & -\frac{\nu_{23}^0}{E_2^0} & \frac{1}{E_3^0} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}^0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{23}^0} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{13}^0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$\underline{\underline{H}} = \sqrt{\underline{\underline{I}} - \underline{\underline{D}}} \quad (10)$$

and where: σ_{ij} are the stress tensor components along the x-y-z global axes; E_1^0, E_2^0 and E_3^0 are the initial Young's moduli; ν_{12}^0, ν_{23}^0 and ν_{13}^0 are the initial Poisson's ratios; G_{12}^0, G_{13}^0 and G_{23}^0 are the initial shear moduli; and $\underline{\underline{\epsilon}}^p$ is plastic (also permanent) strain tensor defined in [10]. It should be noted that in this case, the square root is one in the same as the component-wise square root given that the matrices are diagonal. The stiffness matrix is that of the on-axis lamina response and is aligned along the 1-2-3 material axes.

1.1.3. Fatigue failure indices

The fatigue failure indices describe a reserve to failure based on the effective stresses and a failure surface. The computation of the fatigue failure index is based on the maximum stress failure criterion:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_{11} &= \frac{|\tilde{\sigma}_{11}|}{X} \\ \Sigma_{22} &= \frac{|\tilde{\sigma}_{22}|}{Y} \\ \Sigma_{12} &= \frac{|\tilde{\sigma}_{12}|}{S} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $\underline{\underline{\tilde{\sigma}}}$ is the effective stress tensor defined by:

$$\underline{\underline{\tilde{\sigma}}} = \left(\underline{\underline{I}} - \underline{\underline{D}} \right)^{-1} \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \quad (12)$$

and the tensor $\underline{\underline{I}}$ is the identity tensor. It should be noted that σ is continuously computed during each simulated cycle, such as to then obtain each cycles minimum and maximum envelope stresses.

In turn, the in-plane longitudinal and transverse lamina strengths, X and Y, are computed according to the stress components, with subscripts c and t indicating a compression and tension, respectively:

$$\begin{aligned} X &= X_T \frac{\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle}{|\sigma_{11}|} + X_C \frac{\langle -\sigma_{11} \rangle}{|\sigma_{11}|} \\ Y &= Y_T \frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle}{|\sigma_{22}|} + Y_C \frac{\langle -\sigma_{22} \rangle}{|\sigma_{22}|} \end{aligned}, \text{ where: } \{X_C, Y_C\} \geq 0 \quad (13)$$

1.1.4. Laws for the evolution of fatigue damage in a unidirectional ply

The laws for the evolution of fatigue damage are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d(d_{11}^+)}{dN} &= C_{1,11} \Delta \Sigma_{11}^+ \exp \left(-C_{2,11} \frac{d_{11}^+}{\sqrt{\Delta \Sigma_{11}^+}} \right) \\ &\quad + C_{3,11} d_{11}^+ \Delta \Sigma_{11}^{+2} \exp(C_{5,11} \langle \Delta \Sigma_{11}^+ - C_{4,11} \rangle) \\ \frac{d(d_{11}^-)}{dN} &= \left[C_{1,11} \Delta \Sigma_{11}^- \exp \left(-C_{2,11} \frac{d_{11}^-}{\sqrt{\Delta \Sigma_{11}^-}} \right) \right]^3 + C_{3,11} d_{11}^- \Delta \Sigma_{11}^{-2} \exp \left(\frac{C_{5,11}}{3} \langle \Delta \Sigma_{11}^- - C_{4,11} \rangle \right) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d(d_{22}^+)}{dN} &= C_{1,22} (1 + D_{12}^{f^2}) \Delta\Sigma_{22}^+ \exp\left(-C_{2,22} \frac{d_{22}^+}{\sqrt{\Delta\Sigma_{22}^+} (1 + D_{12}^2)}\right) \\ &\quad + C_{3,22} d_{22}^+ \Delta\Sigma_{22}^{+2} \exp(C_{5,22} \langle \Delta\Sigma_{22}^+ - C_{4,22} \rangle) \\ \frac{d(d_{22}^-)}{dN} &= \left[C_{1,22} (1 + D_{12}^{f^2}) \Delta\Sigma_{22}^- \exp\left(-C_{2,22} \frac{d_{22}^-}{\sqrt{\Delta\Sigma_{22}^-} (1 + D_{12}^2)}\right) \right]^{1+2\exp(-D_{12}^{f^2})} \\ &\quad + C_{3,22} d_{22}^- \Delta\Sigma_{22}^{-2} \exp\left(\frac{C_{5,22}}{3} \langle \Delta\Sigma_{22}^- - C_{4,22} \rangle\right)\end{aligned}\quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d(d_{12}^+)}{dN} &= C_{1,12} (1 + (d_{12}^-)^2) \Delta\Sigma_{12}^+ \exp\left(-C_{2,12} \frac{d_{12}^+}{2\sqrt{\Delta\Sigma_{12}^+} (1 + (d_{12}^-)^2)}\right) \\ &\quad + C_{3,12} d_{12}^+ \Delta\Sigma_{12}^{+2} \exp(C_{5,12} \langle \Delta\Sigma_{12}^+ - C_{4,12} \rangle) \\ \frac{d(d_{12}^-)}{dN} &= C_{1,12} (1 + (d_{12}^+)^2) \Delta\Sigma_{12}^- \exp\left(-C_{2,12} \frac{d_{12}^-}{2\sqrt{\Delta\Sigma_{12}^-} (1 + (d_{12}^+)^2)}\right) \\ &\quad + C_{3,12} d_{12}^- \Delta\Sigma_{12}^{-2} \exp(C_{5,12} \langle \Delta\Sigma_{12}^- - C_{4,12} \rangle)\end{aligned}\quad (16)$$

where $C_{i,j}$ are material coefficients ($i = 1,5$ and $j = 11, 22$ or 12) and,

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\Sigma_{ij}^+ &= \max_t \left(\Sigma_{ij} \frac{\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle}{|\sigma_{ij}|} \right) \\ \Delta\Sigma_{ij}^- &= \max_t \left(\Sigma_{ij} \frac{\langle -\sigma_{ij} \rangle}{|\sigma_{ij}|} \right)\end{aligned}\quad (17)$$

1.1.5. Plastic strain accumulation

Van Papegem observed the occurrence of plastic shear strains due to the accumulation of shear damage [10]. Some matrix debris formed under in-plane shear accumulates in matrix cracks that open when plies are loaded in tension. The following evolution law was developed to capture this mechanism,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\gamma_{12}^p}{dN} = C_9 \max_{t \leq T} \langle \gamma_{12} \rangle \frac{dd_{12}^+}{dN} - C_9 \max_{t \leq T} \langle -\gamma_{12} \rangle \frac{dd_{12}^-}{dN} \\ \varepsilon_{11}^p = \varepsilon_{22}^p = \varepsilon_{33}^p = \gamma_{13}^p = \gamma_{23}^p = 0 \end{cases}\quad (1)$$

where C_9 is a material coefficient.

1.2. Objectives

The aim of this report is to document the implementation of the semi-empirical modelling approach developed by van Papegem [10] to capture the evolution of interlaminar fatigue damage in a unidirectional GFRP laminate. It is part (task 5.2) of the integrated simulation framework of the EU Horizon 2020 UPWARDS Project. Importantly, this intralaminar model uses the cycle- or N-jump approach, which makes it compatible with the inter-laminar model implemented in Task 5.1.

To this end, a robust and efficient industrial parameter identification tool is developed in the non-linear Simcenter Samcef FE code to determine, check and refine the model's many material parameters. The semi-empirical approach reverse-engineers the parameters based on flexural fatigue testing data obtained from a set of five specific laminate layups designed to capture the three types of intralaminar fatigue damage: longitudinal, transverse and in-plane shear, and combinations thereof. In turn, a four-point loading configuration is used in contrast to previous work, which used a three-point configuration [11], to obtain a more uniform flexural stress state in the coupon mid-span.

Unlike tensile testing, flexural testing allows for the testing of the five laminate configurations to be load-independent, thereby significantly reducing the amount and duration of testing required. Though previous research still relied on fatigue data obtained in tension to set fatigue loading levels

for each flexural test configuration [11], in this report, load levels are instead estimated based on a couple of exploratory fatigue specimens and the A-basis allowable of the flexural strength obtained from a short static testing program. This approach is suitable while still considerably reducing the amount and duration of experimental testing.

Lastly, the identified parameters and the overall performance of the model is validated against fatigue testing data obtained from a laminate with a more complex stacking sequence (i.e. quasi-isotropic) that is akin to layups used in industrial structures such as wind turbines. Such a layup results in a non-uniform stress field through-the-thickness. In addition, Digital image correlation (DIC) is employed to compare FEM predictions of the through-the-thickness strain with experimental measurements, as well as to inform on the suitability of the composite material used for the overall exercise.

2. Methodology

2.1. Mechanical testing

2.1.1. Test configuration and setup

The parameter identification for the intralaminar fatigue model relies on flexural fatigue testing data using a four-point loading configuration. No standardized test method currently addresses the fatigue testing of composite laminates in flexure. This report instead relies on method B of the ISO 14125 standardized test method for quasi-static flexural testing of fibre-reinforced polymers [12], which specifies the coupon and loading geometries for a four-point loading configuration with support points set at one third of the outer support span. Fig. 3 presents a schematic of a coupon inserted into the four-point flexure fixture.

The support points are low-friction rollers with a nominal radius, R , of 9.0 mm, which are fitted with internal roller bearings. A high-performance grade of stainless steel (PH13-8 MO) is selected given the abrasive nature of the debris that can be generated during flexural testing of GFRP. The rollers are machined to a polished finish and then heat treated (H950 protocol) to a Rockwell hardness of approximately C30, which has proven to be sufficiently high. The waisted profile of the outer (lower) rollers acts as a guide to prevent sideways shifting of coupons during cyclical testing.

It should be noted that the use of waisted rollers may introduce small lateral loads in the event of coupon shifting during testing, which is unavoidable when using lateral coupon guides or constraints. This risk is however minimized by only utilizing such rollers for the outer rollers and by limiting the depth of the waisted profile half of a nominal ply thickness (0.5 mm). It should be further noted that no end stops are implemented as no axial shifting (or walking) of coupons is expected during fatigue testing. For one, the laminates all have a relatively rough vacuum-bag side due to the use of a peel-ply during the cure. Second, coupons are never fully unloaded during testing.

In turn, the roller support blocks and the T-slot beams are CNC-milled out of high-strength 7075 aluminium to reduce the inertia of the fixture while retaining appropriate stiffness. Next, the fixture is equipped with a laser triangulation displacement sensor (model: optoNCDT 1420-25) manufactured by Micro-Epsilon Messtechnik GmbH & Co, Germany. A contactless sensor such as a laser is preferable to track the mid-span deflection, s , in the case of fatigue testing. Its measuring range spans from a height of 25 to 50 mm over the laser interface on the unit. It should be noted that coupons are installed with the rougher vacuum-bag side facing up and the smoother tool side down to minimize the effect of surface roughness on laser measurements. A small fan is additionally trained onto the sensor to keep testing debris from blocking the laser beam. Finally, the fixture is setup on an Instron 8801 hydraulic fatigue testing machine fitted with a 10 kN load-cell.

Fig. 3. Schematic of the four-point flexure test fixture.

2.1.2. Materials and coupon preparation

The GFRP laminates tested as part of this work were manufactured by Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy A/S, Denmark. The reinforcement architecture consists of a stacking sequence of UD non-crimp fabric (NCF) layers that are infused with a toughened epoxy resin. The NCF itself consists of 90 wt.% of high-modulus (HM) glass fibre roving (or bundles) that are stitched together. The nominal cured ply thickness is approximately 1 mm. Further details regarding the constituents and processing method cannot be divulged as they are currently being used by SIEMENS in its wind turbine blade production.

Table 1 lists the six laminate stacking sequences. The first five laminates are reserved to generate test data for the parameter identification of the intralaminar fatigue model. In turn, the sixth laminate is reserved for validation of the identified parameters and overall model performance, which is discussed in greater detail in Sect. 2.3. It should be noted that the coupon and test axes run parallel to the global Cartesian x axis (Fig. 3). Principal material axes are not utilized because four of the six laminates contain more than one ply orientation.

Table 1. Laminate stacking sequences.

Test order	Reference code	Description	Stacking sequence	Purpose
1	U	Unidirectional	$[0^\circ]_{2s}$	Model parameter identification
2	O45	$\pm 45^\circ$ off-axis	$[\pm 45^\circ]_s$	
3	T	Transverse	$[90^\circ]_{2s}$	
4	X	Cross-ply	$[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$	
5	O30	$\pm 30^\circ$ off-axis	$[\pm 30^\circ]_s$	
6	Q	Quasi-isotropic	$[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$	Model validation

The coupon and loading geometries of the first five laminates are loosely based on specimen Class III and Annex A of ISO 14125 [12]. The nominal thickness of 4 mm requires a doubling of proportions and spans. In addition, the prescribed width was increased to 20 mm such as to include a minimum of five fibre bundles across the width of 0° plies to ensure representative results that are reproducible between coupons. Table 2 lists the coupon and loading configuration geometries.

Care is taken during the coupon preparation to ensure that the width and thickness standard deviations are below 3% and 2%, respectively, for any given laminate sample. Length and width measurements are taken with a digital Vernier calliper accurate to 10 μ m, and thickness

measurements are taken with a digital micrometre accurate to 1 μm . First, coupon strips with a width set to the coupon length ($l = 150 \text{ mm}$) are cut from the laminate sheets using an industrial tile saw. Individual coupons are then cut from each strip using a Struers Unitom-5 cut-off machine fitted with a Struers diamond cut-off wheel (model: 26EXO). Finally, coupon edges are manually ground with a wetted P1200 SiC sandpaper on a flat surface to a uniformly fine finish. The coupons are kept in a standard laboratory environment for at least one week prior to testing ($23 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $50 \pm 10\%$ humidity).

Table 2. Coupon and loading configuration geometries.

Nominal values (mm)	Laminate	
	U, O45, T, X, and O30	Q
Thickness, h	4	8
Width, b	20*	20*
Length, l	150*	150*
Outer span, L	90	120*
Inner span, L'	30	40*
Outer span-to-thickness ratio, L/h	22,5	15*
Inner span to thickness ratio, L'/h	7,5	5*

* Deviation from the ISO 14125 standardized test method [1].

2.1.3. Quasi-static testing method

The fatigue testing is to be performed in load control with the load cycling between constant lower and upper load limits. These load limits are derived from the selected loading fraction for a given laminate, which is the ratio of the maximum applied flexural stress and the laminate's flexural strength. It is critical to set a loading fraction that is sufficiently low as to avoid imparting static damage during the first fatigue cycle, because the intralaminar fatigue model should only be fed intralaminar fatigue data for correct parameters to be identified. A secondary, practical consideration is to reduce the test duration to less than one day or approximately 50k cycles.

A program of quasi-static testing is therefore performed prior to fatigue testing to determine appropriate loading fractions for each laminate. The speed of testing, v , is set to 1 mm/min for all tests, and a minimum of five coupons are tested per laminate. In turn, a small temporary load of <50 N is applied upon installing a coupon in the fixture and prior to launching the test to let the coupon shift axially and settle between rollers. This step ensures that the inner rollers sit in local valleys on the rougher specimen side, thereby yielding a smoother load curve during the test.

The mean flexural modulus, E_f , and the strength at break, σ_{fB} , are the main material properties determined for each sample. It should be noted, for the purposes of this report, that static failure is defined as the onset of damage rather than full coupon rupture. It is typically characterized by a small load drop on the load-deflection curve due to matrix cracking and fibre breakage. The A-basis allowable of the flexural strength, σ_{f99} , is then computed for each sample by feeding the individual coupon strength values into the A- & B-Basis Analysis Software (version 1.3) developed by Centre Composite, Latvia [13]. The software is itself based on the statistical methods (including several corrections) published in volume one of the US Military's Composite Materials Handbook [14]. The A-basis allowable is a statistical material property calculated for a given sample population that 99% of tested specimens will exceed with a 95% confidence interval. It is therefore expected that only 1 in 100 coupons will fail when subjected to σ_{f99} .

The A-basis allowable represents the maximum flexural stress level, $\sigma_{f,max}$, to be used for fatigue testing, from which the upper load level can be calculated using Simple Beam Theory. An additional unit knockdown factor, K , can be applied to ensure a sufficiently long fatigue life for the purpose of the parameter identification, i.e. a minimum of several hundred cycles. The loading fraction, LF , can then be defined as:

$$LF = K \cdot \sigma_{fA} / \sigma_{f99} = \sigma_{f,max} / \sigma_{fB} \quad (18)$$

A final point of consideration is the fact that the flexural stress-strain behaviour of both off-axis laminates, O45 and O30, is non-linear as it is dominated by matrix properties. Significant stiffness degradation and plastic strain accumulation are expected to appear at relatively low stress levels. It is preferable to limit the extent of this static damage in the first fatigue cycle by selecting an appropriately low loading fraction. Additional sets of quasi-isotropic hysteresis testing are therefore conducted with incremental unloading-loading loops performed every 100 N and 200 N for the O45 and O30 laminates, respectively. The loading and unloading test speeds are set at 1 and 5 mm/min, respectively, and a minimum of five coupons are again tested per laminate. Fig. 4 illustrates the typical hysteresis testing results for a single coupon test.

Fig. 4. Typical hysteresis testing results for a single coupon test.

Appropriate loading fractions can be selected from plots of the stiffness degradation and plastic strain accumulation as functions of the peak hysteresis stress per hysteresis cycle. First, individual coupon datasets are combined and sorted for a given sample. The combined datasets are then fitted to estimate the degree of static damage for a given stress level, which corresponds to $\sigma_{f,max}$ for a given K value (Eq. A). Such plots are presented in Sect. 3.1.1 along with the quasi-static testing results.

2.1.4. Fatigue testing method

The fatigue testing is performed under load-control in sinusoidal mode, which is well suited to the loading configuration and easier on the test machine. Fig. 5 illustrates a sine waveform with constant frequency, f , and amplitude, A_f . As described in the previous section, the upper load limit, F_{max} , is selected for each sample based on the results of the quasi-static ramp and hysteresis testing programs. In turn, the lower load limit, F_{min} , is calculated using Simple Beam Theory from the minimum flexural stress level, $\sigma_{f,min}$, which is itself set as a fixed load ratio, R , of the maximum flexural stress level:

$$\sigma_{f,min} = R \cdot \sigma_{f,max} \quad (19)$$

For the purposes of this work, R is set for all tests to a small fixed value of 0.1 to ensure that coupons are continuously loaded during testing. This value is often used in fatigue testing of composites, when a nearly complete loading-unloading cycle is desired [15-18].

Fig. 5. Schematic of the sinusoidal waveform used for fatigue testing in load-control.

The cycle frequency is another critically important test parameter. It has been demonstrated that glass fibres are strain rate dependent [16], and that matrix dominated systems, e.g. off-axis laminates, can show significant hysteresis heating above a test frequency of 4 Hz [16-19]. Limited evidence suggests that GFRP can safely be tested in four-point flexure at elevated frequencies up to 80 Hz with increases in temperature below 15 °C [20]. Nevertheless, a frequency of 2.0 Hz is selected to minimize both phenomena. Similar values have been selected in studies investigating the flexural fatigue of GFRP laminates [7, 21]. An infrared thermometer was trained at various points on the surface of exploratory coupons tested under the following conditions: $f = 2.0$ Hz, $K = 0.9$ and $R = 0.1$. No temperatures greater than $4 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ above ambient room temperature were recorded, which dismisses concerns over hysteresis heating posing a problem.

The test procedure is implemented in Instron's WaveMatrix dynamic testing software (version 1.8). Table 3 lists the test segments in chronological order. Two types of datasets are recorded during the various test segments: tracking points and cycle peaks. Tracking points are recorded during the execution of single waveforms, i.e. a single ramp or sinusoidal cycle, with a data reduction rate of 2 pts/s for ramps and 20 pts per cycle. In particular, cycle tracking data is recorded at prescribed cycle and laser reading increments (e.g. every 1k cycles and changes of more than 0.1 mm, respectively) to capture the evolution of the plastic strain during the fatigue life of O45 coupons, which is discussed in Sect. 3.2.2.

Table 3. Fatigue test procedure.

Order	Step	Data recording	Purpose
1	Preload ramp: 0 N \rightarrow F_{\min} at 20 N/s	None	
2	Quasi-static load ramp: $F_{\min} \rightarrow F_{\max}$ at 10 N/s	Tracking: 2 pts/s	First cycle (2-3): check for static damage
3	Unload ramp: $F_{\max} \rightarrow F_{\min}$ at 20 N/s	Peaks: min and max	
4	Pause: hold at F_{\min}	N/a	
5	Sinusoidal cycling: $F_{\min} \leftrightarrow F_{\max}$ at 2 Hz	Tracking: 20 pts/cycle ^{a, b} Peaks: min and max per cycle ^a	Fatigue loading until break at N_B cycles
6	Test stoppage: actuator off	N/a	

^a Recording at prescribed cycle and laser reading increments. ^b Data intended for the analysis of O45 coupons only.

In turn, cycle peaks are defined as the minimum and maximum machine displacements during a single waveform. This dataset is also recorded at prescribed cycle and laser reading increments. The setting of recording increments is based on user experience as well as the fatigue curve of one

or more exploratory specimen per sample such as to generate sufficiently sampled fatigue curves and hysteresis tracking datasets.

The test procedures begin with a preload ramp up to the minimum load limit. The coupon is then subjected to a quasi-static load ramp up to the upper load limit and is subsequently unloaded back to the lower load limit to check that no static damage is imparted during the first loading cycle. Once the specimen and load-deflection data has been inspected, the operator launches the sinusoidal cyclic loading of the coupon. The test is finally ended once one of the machine crosshead, load cell or laser limits is tripped, which indicates specimen break at N_B cycles, i.e. the coupon's fatigue life. As an aside, setting conservative limits to ensure personnel health and safety is one the most important steps during the setup of these experiments other than carefully tuning the PID control parameters of the testing machine, which varies with stiffness for every laminate configuration. Hydraulic dynamic test machines can move at very high speeds with very short response times.

2.2. Intra-laminar fatigue modelling

2.2.1. Finite element model implementation

The intralaminar model is implemented in the non-linear Simcenter Samcef FE code as a behaviour law as detailed in this section. Of note, several features are developed to render the model usable for FE analysis.

Cycle-jump computation

Samcef has developed an equivalent procedure to the cycle-jump approach described in [10] to perform the fatigue analysis in a more computationally efficient manner in terms of CPU time. The simulation skips cycles over which negligible stiffness degradation is deemed to occur. The damage evolution is instead updated at cycle increments, over which significant damage occurs, using an explicit computational scheme. The stress and stiffness matrices are computed during each significant cycle assuming constant damage throughout a given cycle. Once a flattening or balancing of the damage curve occurs, the number of cycles to jump, N_{JUMP1} , is estimated for each integration point according to the derivative, dD/dN . At this stage, the code performs a statistical analysis of all integration point cycle jumps and identifies a global cycle jump, N_{JUMP} . The damage is finally extrapolated after N_{JUMP} cycles.

The significant damage growth criterion, ΔD , is proposed in [10] as a one dimensional state:

$$\Delta D = D_{N+N_{JUMP1}} - D_N = \begin{cases} 10^{-20} & \text{if } D = 0 \\ 0.5D & \text{if } 0 < D \leq 0.2 \\ 0.1 & \text{if } D > 0.2 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

$$N_{JUMP1} = \frac{\Delta D}{\left. \frac{dD}{dN} \right|_N} \quad (21)$$

The computation of N_{JUMP1} only considers the most dominant of three intralaminar components: D_{11} , D_{12} and D_{13} . The damage accumulation and rate are the respective sum of d_{ij}^+ and d_{ij}^- and their corresponding rates.

Parameters

The required material parameters used for the intralaminar fatigue model are listed in Table 4 along with the corresponding variable names used in the code.

Table 4. List of the required material parameters for the intralaminar fatigue damage model.

No.	Samtech	Code variable	Description
1	E ₁	YT(1)	Young modulus in 1 direction
2	E ₂	YT(2)	Young modulus in 2 direction
3	E ₃	YT(3)	Young modulus in 3 direction
4	G ₁₂	G(1)	Shear Stress modulus
5	G ₂₃	G(2)	Shear Stress modulus
6	G ₁₃	G(3)	Shear Stress modulus
7	v ₁₂	NT(1)	Poisson ratio
8	v ₂₂	NT(2)	Poisson ratio
9	v ₁₃	NT(3)	Poisson ratio
10	X _T	XT(1)	Stress limit in tension in 1 direction
11	Y _T	XT(2)	Stress limit in tension in 2 direction
12	X _C	XC(1)	Stress limit in compression in 1 direction
13	Y _C	XC(2)	Stress limit in compression in 2 direction
14	S	RST(1)	Stress limit in shear
15	d _{max}	DDEN	Fatigue damage parameter limit (default value 0.999)
16-20	C _{i,11} (i = 1..5)	CFAT(1 : 5)	Fatigue damage parameter
21-25	C _{i,22} (i = 1..5)	CFAT(6 :10)	Fatigue damage parameter
26-30	C _{i,12} (i = 1..5)	CFAT(11 :15)	Fatigue damage parameter
31	C ₉	CFAT(16)	Fatigue permanent strain coefficient
32	h	HPN	Crack closure effect on stiffness reduction

Initial static damage and total damage tensor

It is possible to impose the initial static damage, \underline{D}_s , discussed in Sect. 1.1.1 in the Samcef FE code using the following command:

```
.CLM support element DA6 value - [comp -] [sply -]
```

Post-processing

The Samcef FE code outputs a number of variables listed in Table 5 along with the corresponding code variables used to set variables in the Samcef solver. These variables describe the intralaminar damage behaviour law for single UD plies of the selected GFRP material. In turn, they are used to compute the deformation field of the CAE model.

Table 5. List of the resultant variables that describe the fatigue damage behaviour law.

Behaviour law variable	Code variable	Components
Equivalent permanent strain γ_{12}^p	*320	*
damage D_{11}^f	*842	1
damage D_{22}^f	*842	2
damage D_{12}^f	*842	4
Σ_{11}	*844	1
Σ_{22}	*844	2
Σ_{12}	*844	4
damage $D_{11}^s + D_{11}^f$	*843	1
damage $D_{22}^s + D_{22}^f$	*843	2
damage $D_{12}^s + D_{12}^f$	*843	4

2.2.2. Model parameter identification tool

The engineering constants and lamina strengths of the selected GFRP material are provided by the material supplier, Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy A/S, Denmark. The task of the model parameter identification tool is to reverse engineer the material-specific fatigue parameters (or

coefficients) required to populate the model (Fig. 6). The stiffness degradation is obtained from the experimental fatigue testing program in the form of an increase in mid-span deflection as a function of cycles. The stiffness is recovered from a FE model into which the deflection-cycle data is fed along with an initial guess for the fatigue coefficients. A numerical stiffness evolution plot is subsequently generated and compared with the experimental one. Finally, the material parameters are manually updated until the FE and experimental curves match.

Fig. 6. Flowchart of the model parameter identification tool.

Each of the five selected layups allows for the identification, verification and refinement of the sets of parameters for the three dominant in-plane damage variables. Table 6 lists the corresponding damage variables and coefficients for each of the five layup configurations in order of operation.

Table 6. Roles of the five layup configurations in the parameter identification.

Step	Configuration	Layup	Dominant damage parameter	Purpose
1	U	$[0^\circ]_{ns}$	D_{11}	Identify $C_{i,11}$
2	O45	$[\pm 45^\circ]_{ns}$	D_{12}	Identify $C_{i,12}$ and possibly C_9
3	T	$[90^\circ]_{ns}$	D_{22}	Identify $C_{i,12}$
4	X	$[0^\circ/90^\circ]_{ns}$	D_{11} (+ D_{22})	Refine $C_{i,11}$; check D_{22}
5	O30	$[\pm 30^\circ]_{ns}$	D_{12} (+ D_{11})	Refine $C_{i,11}$ and C_9 ; check D_{11}/D_{12}

Finally, the various coefficients apply to different stages of the fatigue curve (Fig. 1) as detailed in [11]. They are therefore identified sequentially over the following segments of the recovered experimental stiffness degradation curve:

- $C_{1,ij}$: first 1% of N_B ;
- $C_{2,ij}$: first 10% of N_B ;
- $C_{3,ij}$: first 80% of N_B ;
- $C_{4,ij}$: stiffness drop between Stages II and III drops;
- $C_{5,ij}$: reproduction of N_B ;
- C_9 : final stiffness drop as $N \rightarrow N_B$.

where N_B is the number of cycles at break. The C_9 coefficient is determined from the experimental hysteresis data (intra-cycle tracking data, Sect. 2.1.4) that is obtained from the O45 layup configuration upon recovering the plastic component of the deflection.

2.3. Model validation method

The five laminates reserved for the model parameter identification have simple stacking sequences aimed to capture the lamina response (Table 1). Experimental validation of the intralaminar fatigue model and the identified material parameters requires a more complex stacking sequence that is representative of structural laminates used in the field. To this end, the ubiquitous

quasi-isotropic layup is selected ($[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_{2S}$) with 0° plies placed at the laminate bottom and top surfaces for maximal flexural stiffness. The nominal laminate thickness is effectively doubled from 4 to 8 mm given the substantial nominal ply thickness of 1 mm. However, the geometric constraints of the fixture require a smaller support span-to-thickness ratio of 15 instead of 22.5, which is a notable departure from ISO 14125 [12]. This ratio is right on the cusp of what is deemed acceptable for flexural testing, i.e. a ratio of 16:1, given the rise of higher shear stresses between top and bottom roller pairs. It will yield satisfactory flexural strength values, which is the targeted output data, but it will not yield reliable flexural stiffness values [22].

Fig. 7. Digital image correlation experimental setup.

As in the case of the first five samples, the static ramp program described in Sect. 2.1.3 is performed to determine a safe upper load limit that will not engender static damage during the first fatigue loading cycle. The same fatigue test methodology described in Sect. 2.1.4 is subsequently followed for the first three of five coupons. The remaining two coupons are tested in a similar fashion with the addition of a digital image correlation (DIC) stereo camera system trained onto the coupon midspan edge to provide strain field evolution throughout the fatigue life. Fig. 7 captures the camera placement relative to the test fixture.

The DIC system consists of four categories of parts: i) video equipment, ii) lighting, iii) data acquisition (DAQ) and mounting hardware, and iv) data acquisition and analysis software including calibration hardware. The specifications and setup for each categories of parts is as follows:

- i. The video equipment consists of two Allied Vision 5-MP CCD cameras (model: Pike F-505B) that are equipped with Pentax 75-mm fixed focal length lenses (model: C37500) and 30-mm extension tubes to further narrow the field of view (FoV) to $15.2 \times 12.7 \text{ mm}^2$ ($2452 \times 2052 \text{ px}^2$). The spatial resolution in the object plane, i.e. the DIC pattern on coupon, is $6.19 \mu\text{m}/\text{px}$. The cameras are rigidly mounted to the test machine frame with an adjustable, custom T-slot aluminium profile frame to reduce rigid body motion and accidental dislocations once calibrated. In turn, the image orientation is set to landscape mode by simply rotating the

cameras to increase the captured coupon span. Next, the cameras are positioned with a stereo angle of $\sim 15^\circ$ in the horizontal plane (defined by the specimen midplane) to ensure that the focal planes of both cameras intersect vertically across the middle of the image—given that the coupon travels vertically in the frame. Lastly, an aperture of $f/11$ is selected to maximize depth of field while minimizing lens diffraction.

- ii. The lighting source is a 30 W LED flood lamp that is installed over the cameras rather than underneath them to eliminate adverse thermal effects. The lamp has a fixed brightness rating of 2,550 lumens and a temperature of 4,000 °K. This level of brightness allows for high-contrast (150-180 mean image intensity) and reasonable exposure time of 18.0 ms at $f/11$, thereby minimizing vibration-induced motion blur.
- iii. The DAQ and camera mounting hardware are sourced and assembled by ISI-SYS GmbH, Germany. In addition to the camera feeds, analogue signals for the machine displacement, load and laser reading are scaled and outputted along with a 5V TTL digital trigger channel to the DIC desktop station via a DAQ unit to match each frame that is grabbed during the test with the corresponding signal values.
- iv. The acquisition software Vic-Snap (version 8), the analysis software Vic-3D™ (version 8.4.0) and the calibration target are produced by Correlated Solutions Inc., USA. The calibration is performed using Correlated Solutions' high-precision etched glass targets (9 × 9 dots, 1.34 mm spacing), a custom pan-tilt target holder and LED backlighting (Fig. 8). A series of 50 image pairs were taken at various pan and tilt angle combinations and analysed in Vic-3D™ to yield a calibration score of 0.028 with a score below 0.03 being very good.

Fig. 8. Pan-tilt holder for glass calibration targets: a) schematic of the holder and its adjustability, and b) calibration target installation on the lower rollers (upper rollers and supports are removed).

Prior to testing, a speckle pattern is painted on each coupon with a dual action airbrush (Harder & Steenbeck Evolution Silverline) fitted with a fine 0.4-mm diameter nozzle. High-pigmentation white and black acrylic inks (Schmincke Aero-Color® Professional) are used for the background and speckles, respectively. Care must be taken in fixing the airbrush parameters to achieve a near-optimal pattern, i.e. homogeneously random speckle distribution across the pattern, with an even distribution of speckle sizes from 4 px to 15 px in diameter to avoid aliasing and subset over-sampling, and a 30-50% background coverage. Practical considerations for the creation of near-optimal DIC speckle patterns are detailed in [23], [24] and [25].

The addition of a DIC system to the experimental setup slightly alters the test procedure detailed in Table 3. The continuous sinusoidal cyclic loading in step 5 is changed to a looping step consisting of a set number of dynamic cycles followed by a slow cycle, during which the cameras are triggered by the Instron system. The number of dynamic cycles per loop is selected based on an exploratory specimen obtain enough camera frames while limiting the size of the recorded image

set, which is important to reduce the post-processing time. In turn, the slow cycle consists of a simple loading ramp, hold and unloading ramp, each lasting 5 sec. The slower cycle speed is necessary to eliminate motion blur and reduce mechanical vibrations acting on the camera sensors. Lastly, the loop is set to repeat until failure occurs, again, by tripping of one of the channel limits.

Fig. 9. DIC analysis setup: a) selected area of interest, and b) resulting Lagrangian e_{xx} strain field.

The data acquisition is performed via Vic-Snap, which records the local clock of the DIC computer and the analogue signals from the Instron test machine for every pair of frames captures by the two cameras. Test images and the initial calibration are then opened in Vic-3D™ for analysis. Fig. 9 displays a selected area of interest (AOI) and the corresponding computed Lagrangian e_{xx} strain field. The setup of the analysis is as follows:

- i. Subset and step sizes of 29 and 5 px, respectively;
- ii. Subset weights: Gaussian;
- iii. Interpolation options:
 - Interpolation: optimized 8-tap,
 - Criterion: normalized square differences,
 - Other selected options: "low-pass filter" and "fill boundary";
- iv. Consistency thresholding: maximum threshold of 0.02 px;
- v. Post processing:
 - Coordinate transformation: auto plane fit,
 - Strain computation: Lagrange tensor type with a filter size of 15 subsets (90% centre-weighted Gaussian filter);
- vi. Removal of rigid body motion.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Mechanical testing results

3.1.1. Quasi-static testing

Quasi-static flexural coupon tests were performed on the five parameter identification and the single model validation layups (Table 1) per the method specified in Sect. 2.1.3. Fig. 10 presents the stress-strain curves for all six layups, which are obtained from the data reduction specified in ISO 14125 [12]. The behaviour is linear for all layups except for the two off-axis ones, i.e. the O45 and O30 configurations. In turn, the test results have a relatively low scatter except for the slopes of the

six coupons tested for layout U, and to a lesser extent the five coupons tested for configuration X. Configurations with external 0°-plies are more sensitive to ply misalignment given flexural elastic responses that are fibre-dominated.

Fig. 10. Flexural stress-strain curves for all six configurations.

A ply misalignment of 1.51° with a standard deviation of 0.142° (16 measurements) was calculated using Fiji's ImageJ software package [26] and a high-resolution scan of the bottom surface of U coupons. The misalignment was taken as the angle created by longitudinal stitches running in parallel to cut-off fibre bundles and the longitudinal coupon edges. It is attributed to operator error during manual layup and resin flow during the infusion process [27]. Despite this source of error, the specimen dimensions were all within the tolerances specified in ISO 14125 [12], and the inner and outer spans were set with a coefficient of variation of less than 1% from nominal values for all tested coupons (Table 2).

Fig. 11. Schematics of the representative quasi-static failure modes for all six configurations.

Inspection of the failed specimen surfaces aided in ascertaining the failure mode for each laminate configuration (Fig. 11). Importantly, a varying albeit significant degree of interlaminar damage was observed in coupons from all six laminates. The stiffer configurations, U and Q, failed in compression including some interlaminar shear delamination and localized fibre crushing from the inner rollers. The exception is configuration X, which failed in interlaminar shear at the 0°/90° interfaces likely spurred by matrix microcracking in the central 90° plies. In turn, the two off-axis

configurations, O45 and O30, failed in tension including some interlaminar shear delamination. Lastly, the weakest configuration, T, failed cleanly in tension.

The failure modes are best understood by closely visualizing the laminate mesostructure, which is relatively complex compared to conventional prepreg tape laminates. Fig. 12 presents a microscopy cross-section of the quasi-isotropic laminate (Q). Fibre bundles are delimited by a distinct interstitial resin network, the bulk of which is intraply. The NCF stitching is also clearly discernible as it threads through resin-rich pockets (Fig. 12a-c). The intraply heterogeneity results in matrix cracks forming between fibre bundles at the bundle or stitching interface rather than within bundles. Delamination cracks eventually ensue as these inter-bundle cracks reach adjacent interply interfaces. Again, the presence of interply stitches facilitates crack propagation this time in the interlaminar plane. It is arguably misleading, then, to refer to this type of damage as purely intraply as it visibly occurs outside of fibre-rich areas. Lastly, the presence of superimposed fibre bundles through-the-thickness, notably in the case of the T and X configurations, is thought to significantly aid the out-of-plane crack propagation.

Fig. 12. Stitched micrographic cross-section of the quasi-isotropic laminate—Q (brightfield illumination; 2-9x magnification; 15° angle slice from the 0° fibre orientation—x axis; strong polarization).

The quasi-static testing program served its primary purpose of providing suitable data, from which to select upper load levels to perform fatigue tests in load control while eliminating the onset of static damage in the first several cycles. Table 7 lists the key static properties that were determined from the test data, as well as the knockdown constants and loading fractions, K and LF , respectively. Values for K are selected based on exploratory fatigue tests for each laminate configuration to obtain enough datapoints per test while restricting the test duration. In addition, hysteresis testing was conducted for both off-axis configurations, O45 and O30, to ensure that the set K values are low enough to limit the extent of non-linear coupon degradation that can be expected during the first fatigue cycle. Fig. 13 presents plots of the stiffness degradation and plastic strain accumulation for combined and sorted datasets (5 coupons ea.). A stiffness degradation and a plastic strain accumulation of less than 10% and 0.01%, respectively, were deemed acceptable for the purposes of this work.

Table 7. Quasi-static testing results for all six configurations.

Configuration	Modulus of elasticity, E_f (GPa)		Strength at break, σ_{fB} (MPa)		A-basis allowable, σ_{f99} (MPa)	Knockdown factor, K	Loading fraction, LF
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
U*	45.5	2.13	3 840	112	921	0.9	0.753
O45	16.0	0.271	215	13.2	139	0.9	0.583
T	13.3	0.222	84.2	5.04	55.3	0.9	0.591
X	38.1	0.960	901	30.9	724	0.7	0.562
O30	23.3	0.526	376	16.8	279	0.8	0.594
Q	30.8	0.551	575	15.3	487	0.8	0.678

* Additional 6th specimen was tested for the modulus determination.

Fig. 13. Quasi-static hysteresis test results for the a) O45 and b) O30 off-axis configurations.

3.1.2. Fatigue testing

Flexural fatigue tests were performed on all six configurations per the method specified in Sect. 2.1.4 and the loading factors that were selected in the previous section (Table 7). Fig. 14 presents history curves of the mid-span deflection in terms of cycles. Though the FEM predictions are included in the figure for the sake of conciseness, the results of the parameter identification and the model validation are presented and discussed in the following Sect. 3.2 and 3.3. In turn, Table 8 presents the number of cycles at break, N_B , and the actual values of the load-control parameters, LF and R, which speak to the accuracy of the Instron test machine in load-control. As was the case for the quasi-static testing, ply misalignment is a known albeit irremediable source of error. However, the specimen dimensions were, again, all within the tolerances specified in ISO 14125 [12], and the inner and outer spans were set with a coefficient of variation of less 1% from nominal values for every tested coupon (Table 2).

First, coupons across laminate configuration generally failed within 50k cycles, which is a relatively short fatigue life as was intended. The exception is the T-configuration coupons, which failed at roughly twice the number of cycles. The longer fatigue life is due to the overly conservative A-basis allowable strengths (σ_{f99}) that were obtained from the quasi-static tests. The datasets used consisted of only five to six σ_{fB} values, whereas ≥ 15 datapoints are typically desirable [14].

In turn, the numbers of cycles at break were marked by large scatters, which many previous experimental and modelling studies and reviews have documented including Degrieck and van Paepegem in [28]. Barnard *et al.* attributed large scatters in UD GFRP laminates to changes in failure modes that manifested as discontinuities in the fatigue curves [29]. The remainder of the scatter can

then be explained by intrinsic variations in static strength properties. Similar discontinuities (sharp upward kinks) can be observed in the fatigue curves of the U, T and Q configurations (Fig. 14), whereby the mode of matrix-cracking changes from intra-ply (inter-bundle) to interply delamination. Once again, it should be noted that the relatively complex mesostructure present in all six laminates is thought to add an additional element of randomness (Fig. 12).

Fig. 14. History curves of the maximum mid-span deflection per cycle and the corresponding FEM predictions for all six configurations.

Table 8. Load-control parameters and cycles at break for all six configurations.

Config.	Loading fraction, LF *			Load ratio, R ^			Break cycle, N _B	
	Mean	CV (%)	Abs. error (%)	Mean	CV (%)	Abs. error (%)	Mean	CV (%)
U	0.778	0.335	3.26	0.0968	0.417	3.15	19.8k	50.3
O45	0.592	0.138	1.56	0.102	0.373	1.59	41.2k	33.6
T	0.588	0.0663	0.582	0.104	0.273	4.06	84.8k	33.6
X	0.569	0.0881	1.33	0.1	0.334	0.278	8.24k	70.9
O30	0.599	0.263	0.83	0.101	0.75	1.16	11.1k	48.3
Q	0.674	0.0805	0.565	0.102	1.4	2.47	10.7k	40.1

* Nominal values are presented in Table D; ^ Nominal value of 0.1.

Lastly, much more pronounced inter-bundle cracking and interlaminar delamination were observed in coupons of all six configurations including changes in failure mode compared to the corresponding quasi-static. Fig. 15 presents schematics of the representative failure modes for each configuration. Configuration U failed in compression under the loading rollers with extensive fibre delamination in the top ply between the upper rollers. However, slightly misaligned fibre bundles on the bottom ply and interrupted by the longitudinal coupon edges also began to peel-off. The three weakest configurations, O45, T and O30, presented with extensive interlaminar delamination between the fibre bundles in bottom plies with some bundles peeling-off at the coupon edges. The greatest change in failure mode was the configuration Q, which failed in interlaminar shear with cracking initiating in the central 90° plies and suddenly propagating at the $\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces. The only configuration with a failure mode that was unchanged was configuration X, which also failed suddenly in interlaminar delamination.

Fig. 15. Schematics of the representative fatigue failure modes for all six laminate configurations.

The lower fatigue loads compared to the corresponding static ones is likely the dominant factor affecting changes in failure mode between static and fatigue loading, which raises the issue of the suitability of the intralaminar modelling approach to predict very low load levels when the materials parameters are determined from relatively high load level tests. Interestingly, the van Paepegem model is itself independent of load level so long as the failure modes remain intralaminar, i.e. the three in-plane damage components: D_{11} , D_{22} and D_{12} , remain dominant.

A more comprehensive fractographic analysis is warranted to better understand the onset and evolution of different failure modes, the impact of the mesostructure and the effect of load level. However, such an analysis extends beyond the scope of the current work. Nevertheless, an important observation can be reached, which is that the evidence of changes in failure modes and the strong interlaminar components are departures from the type of intralaminar failure that the fatigue prediction model was developed to capture [7]. The next two sections discuss the suitability of the experimental data in identifying model parameters and predicting the deflection-cycle history of the more complex and representative Q-laminate configuration.

3.2. Inverse parameter identification

3.2.1. FE model implementation.

A numerical model of the four-point flexure experiment was created and parametrized via the computer-aided engineering (CAE) software Simcenter (version 12), and the FE analyses were subsequently carried out via the Samcef Solver. Exact coupon geometries and loading spans were inputted to the FE model for each test to ensure a high degree of fidelity between experiments and FEM predictions, given that the idealization limits of CAE modelling.

Geometry and mesh

The nominal coupon and loading geometries are listed in Table 2 and illustrated in Fig. 3. Fig. 16 illustrates the CAE implementation of these geometries in Simcenter along with the key contact

and boundary conditions. The laminate is meshed with first-order hexahedral composite elements with one element through-the-thickness of each ply. Elements measure 2 mm in the transverse coupon direction, while bias seeding is implanted in the longitudinal direction to refine the mesh under the loading rollers. Next The rollers are modelled as rigid surfaces (not shown in Fig. 16) and linked by two 1D rigid link elements, one for the upper rollers and the other for the bottom rollers (shown as dashed green arrows).

Fig. 16. CAE implementation in Simcenter of the four-point flexural test.

Material definition

Engineering constants	Identified material parameters
!=====	abre '/c111' '1.E-4'
! Material parameters	abre '/c211' '80.'
!=====	abre '/c311' '4.E-4'
abre '/E11' '45000.'	abre '/c411' '0.92'
abre '/E22' '13303'	abre '/c511' '5.6E2'
abre '/E33' '13303'	
abre '/nu12' '0.31'	abre '/c122' '5.E-4'
abre '/nu13' '0.25'	abre '/c222' ' 2.E+1'
abre '/nu23' '0.28'	abre '/c322' '1.E-4'
abre '/G12' '4530'	abre '/c422' '0.0'
abre '/G23' '1500'	abre '/c522' '0.0'
abre '/G13' '2200'	
abre '/xt1' '1102'	abre '/c112' ' 4.E-4'
abre '/xt2' '84.2'	abre '/c212' '3.E+1'
abre '/xcl' '824.'	abre '/c312' '1.E-6'
abre '/xc2' '167.8'	abre '/c412' '0.9'
abre '/S' '107.5'	abre '/c512' '1.E+4'
	abre '/c9' '1.74'
	abre '/hpn' '0.2.'
	abre '/opt1' '0'
	abre '/opt2' '0'
	abre '/opt3' '0'
	abre '/opt4' '0'
	abre '/DDEN' '0.999'

Fig. 17. FE code entry of the material properties and model parameters for a UD ply.

All the material properties and parameters pertaining to the stacking sequence, ply thicknesses and draping method are defined using the layup option in Simcenter. The constitutive model for a UD ply is also specified in this same option. The material parameters must be entered directly in the bank file as the intralaminar fatigue model utilized in this report is not yet available in the Simcenter graphical user interface. Fig. 17 lists the command lines used to enter the material engineering constants and strengths and the identified material parameters. In all, sixteen parameters need to

be identified. Lastly, the damage limit, DDEN (i.e. d_{\max}), is set to a near unitary value 0.999 as explained in Sect. 1.1.1.

Boundary conditions

The bottom rollers are fully constrained while the top rollers are permitted to travel vertically. A downward force, F , is applied to load the specimen at its mid-span and -width. This force is set to cycle between the F_{\min} and F_{\max} (Fig. 5) and is setup as yet another parametrized variable to account for the different load levels between coupons and layups. In turn, the contacts between the roller and the specimen are modelled without friction. Lastly, central bottom surface node is fixed in y , and the central bottom surface nodes across the width are fixed in x , to ensure that the model is iso-static such as to avoid rigid body motion (Fig. 16).

Fatigue solver parameters

For the classical nonlinear analysis, the solver parameters are entered in the .SUB command as shown in Fig. 18. Most of these parameters are also parametrized. To this end, the static non-linear solver (MECA 22) is setup to run in parallel (RESO 6). The fatigue analysis is activated by the TYJUMP1 variable given a total number of cycles, NCYC, to compute. A loading function is additionally defined and fixed as follows between 0 to 1:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Time} = 0: & \quad F = F_{\min} \\ \text{Time} = 0.5: & \quad F = F_{\max} \\ \text{Time} = 1: & \quad F = F_{\min} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The size of the time step is fixed at 0.5, while other advanced parameters related to the convergence threshold can be modified by the user (i.e. PRCR, PRCE and ITMA).

Advanced parameters	.SUB command
!=====	.SUB
! Mecano parameters	I 1 NAME "Subcase - Nonlinear 1"
!=====	! Analysis Type
abre '/ITMA' '15'	MECA 22 ! Static without initial assembly
abre '/PRCR' '0.005'	! Computation Time and Initial Step
abre '/PRCE' '0.005'	CIBL 1 !Automatic time step
abre '/DTI0' '0.5'	Time 0 0.5 1. (/NCYCLE)
abre '/HMAX' '0.5'	HMIN /hmin
abre '/HMIN' '.5'	HMAX /hmax
	DTAR 0
	IA16 10
	IA4 10
	IA19 1
	! Other Parameters
	PRCR /prcr
	PRCE /prce
	PRCQ 1
	ITMA /itma
	DTI0 /dti0
	LDYN 0
	LSTA 0
	! NJUMP parameters
	TYJUMP (/TYJ)
	CYCB 0.
	CYCE 1.
	NCYC (/NCYCLE)

Fig. 18. Definition of the fatigue solver parameters.

3.2.2. Results of the parameter identification tool

The parameter identification tool identified sixteen parameters to populate the intralaminar fatigue damage model for the selected GFRP material. This section presents and discusses the step-by-step parameter identification process (Table 6), which uses the experimental deflection-

cycle data generated in the previous section. The comprehensive reference written by van Paepegem [11] for this modelling approach ought to be consulted for a greater understanding of how each parameter influences the shape of the stiffness degradation curve.

Step 1: Identification of the $C_{i,11}$ parameters using configuration U

The five $C_{i,11}$ parameters related to the longitudinal damage component, D_{11} , were first to be sequentially identified in accordance to the iterative process described in Fig. 6, starting with $C_{1,11}$ and ending with $C_{5,11}$. Table 9 lists the sequence of operation and the corresponding simulated cycles and initial coefficient values used. For each operation, the previously determined coefficient—if any—were fixed at the newly identified value, the coefficient being determined was set at the guess value, and the remaining coefficients—if any—were set at 0 except for coefficient $C_{4,11}$ and $C_{5,11}$, which must be identified together. Coefficient $C_{4,11}$ should be initially set to the guess value of 1 in the first operation, and its value should then be reduced in subsequent operations to determine an appropriate damage acceleration moment. In turn, coefficient $C_{5,11}$ should be initially set to the guess value of 100, and its value can then be increased or decreased in to determine an appropriate damage acceleration level. It should further be noted that the range of simulated cycles was augmented for each subsequent operation from the first 1% to the full extent of the experimental deflection-cycle curves that were fed into the model. Lastly, the fourth operation is not necessary if the interlaminar shear (ILS) damage mode is observed during the tests.

Table 9. Identification steps for $C_{1,11}$.

Sequence	Fatigue parameters	Range of simulated cycles	Guess
1	$C_{1,11}$	First 1% of N_B	10^{-4}
2	$C_{2,11}$	First 10% of N_B	100
3	$C_{3,11}$	First 80% of N_B	10^{-4}
4	$C_{4,11} / C_{5,11}$	Up to failure	1 / 100

The five identified $C_{i,11}$ parameters associated with the first longitudinal fatigue damage variable, D_{11} , are detailed in Table 10. These parameters offer a good agreement between the FE model predictions and the experimental data as shown in Fig. 14a, notably for stage I and stage II of the fatigue curve (Fig. 1). As for stage III, the identified values for $C_{4,11}$ and $C_{5,11}$ produce a reasonable agreement when set conservatively to 0. However, it is unclear if the failure mode in stage III is intralaminar due evidence of interlaminar damage in failed coupons (Fig. 15), in which case stage III of the experimental curves is not required for the determination of the D_{11} coefficients.

Table 10. Identified $C_{i,11}$ parameters.

$C_{1,11}$	$C_{2,11}$	$C_{3,11}$	$C_{4,11}$	$C_{5,11}$
1×10^{-4}	80	4×10^{-4}	0.92	560

Finally, the predicted damage propagation for D_{11} is presented in Fig. 19 for the top and bottom 0° plies. No significant compressive damage (D_{11}^-) arises in the top ply prior to the 20,961th cycle given a cubic exponent in the initiation phase. The stiffness degradation is instead driven by tensile damage (D_{11}^+) in the bottom ply. At the 21,924th, numerical singularities appear between the contact elements and extensive damage has propagated in both the bottom and top plies. The predicted failure mode does not agree well with the experimental observations due in part to idealization errors. For one, the CAE implementation does not adequately capture stress-concentration of the top rollers acting on the top ply (Fig. 15), which first manifests early in stage II as local fibre bundle during stage II, and which eventually extends later in stage II to longitudinal intraply cracking and interlaminar delamination cracks propagating inward between the two top plies.

Fig. 19. Predicted D_{11} damage propagation for configuration U.

Step 2: Identification of the C_9 and $C_{i,12}$ parameters using configuration O45

The next parameter to be identified was coefficient C_9 , which governs the accumulation of the plastic strain, γ_{12}^p (Sect. 1.1.5). The approach relies on experimental cycle tracking (or hysteresis) data collected per the method described in Sect. 2.1.4. First, the experimental relationship between the plastic strain and the flexural stress was approximated by a polynomial function, from which the initial plastic strain at peak load, $\gamma_{12,i}^p$, was obtained. A mean strain value of $\gamma_{12,i}^p = 0.072\%$ was recovered for a mean flexural load of $\sigma_f = 127$ MPa for the five tested coupons. Next, the corresponding initial plastic component, s_p , of the coupon deflection was then calculated to an average 0325 mm. This value was then manually added to the maximum mid-span deflection data, s_{max} , for each simulated cycle. This operation had to be carried out post simulation given that no static damage model has been implemented in the fatigue modelling framework developed herein.

Fig. 20 presents the flexural stress-strain curves extracted from the first four cycles of coupon no. 6 (Fig. 14b). Linear trendlines were approximated for each hysteresis loop, which allows for the corresponding stiffness and plastic strain to be obtained. Coefficient C_9 is predicted from cycle 345 to 2,119 seeing as the stiffness rises during the first 345 cycles due to fibre scissoring, i.e. re-orienting in the longitudinal direction via stretching of the coupon. Finally, the following formulation was used to compute C_9 for all five coupons, which produced a mean value of $C_9 = 1.74$.

$$C_9 = d\gamma_{12}^p / dd_{12}^+ / \max_{t \leq T} \langle \gamma_{12} \rangle \quad (23)$$

Fig. 20. Hysteresis stress-strain curve and loop stiffness fitting for coupon O45-6.

The five $C_{i,12}$ parameters related to the in-plane shear damage component, D_{12} , were sequentially identified following the same process as described for the five $C_{i,11}$ parameters. Table 11 lists the identified values and the simulated mid-span deflection curve is given in Fig. 14b. Again, a good correlation between predicted and experimental deflection-cycle curves is observed. However, the sudden failure observed in stage III of the experimental curves cannot be reproduced with conservative values for $C_{4,12}$ and $C_{5,12}$, which capture the damage accumulation rate and level from stages II to III. Negligible disparity is apparent between experimental and predicted results even though the two parameters are set to 0. Experimental observations indicated that the sudden failure is mainly due to the interlaminar rather than in-plane shear. Consequently, the D_{12} damage variable likely cannot capture the final drop in stiffness and the full failure of the selected GFRP material.

Table 11. Identified $C_{i,12}$ parameters.

$C_{1,12}$	$C_{2,11}$	$C_{3,12}$	$C_{4,12}$	$C_{5,12}$
4×10^{-4}	30	1×10^{-6}	0.9	1×10^4

Finally, Fig. 21 maps the propagation of the in-plane shear damage component, D_{12} , for the bottom and top 45° plies. Similar damage level evolves on both sides transferring from the coupon edges to the internal plies. Again, the failure mode in the Stage III is not accurately predicted by the model as the damage observed in failed coupons is concentrated in the bottom two plies and includes a dominant interlaminar shear component (Fig. 15).

Fig. 21. Predicted D_{12} damage propagation for configuration O45.

Step 3: Identification of the $C_{i,22}$ parameters using configuration T

The parameter identification procedure for the $C_{i,22}$ coefficients of the transverse damage variable, D_{22} , is the same as the one use for the $C_{i,11}$ and $C_{i,12}$ coefficients. The identified fatigue parameters during this process are listed in Table 12. Configuration T ($[90^\circ]_{2s}$) differs significantly from the first two configurations, U and O45, in that no significant stiffness degradation occurs during the initial cycles. Instead of a distinct stage I, the fatigue curves display a prolonged stage II marked by relatively uniform degradation rates (Fig. 14c). As a result, the predicted failure curve reaches failure prematurely, even though the damage accumulation rate and level coefficients, $C_{4,22}$ and $C_{5,22}$, are set conservatively to 0. Despite this shortcoming, the predicted curve has the right shape in terms notably and notably appears to be capturing the shape of stage III better than for the first two configurations.

A likely explanation for the premature predicted failure is an underestimated value for the transverse tensile strength, Y_t , which leads to a greater initial failure index and earlier failure. This could be due to the significant presence of intraply resin pockets akin to the increase in through-thickness strength observed in GFRP containing thick resin interlayers [26]. A much better

agreement can indeed be had by simply increasing the strength from the manufacturer provided value of $Y_{t1} = 84.2$ MPa to a superior arbitrary value of $Y_{t2} = 200$ MPa, which greatly prolongs the stage II degradation part of the fatigue curve.

Table 12. Identified $C_{i,22}$ parameters.

$C_{1,22}$	$C_{2,21}$	$C_{3,22}$	$C_{4,22}$	$C_{5,22}$
5×10^{-4}	20	1×10^{-4}	0.9	1×10^4

Finally, Fig. 22 maps the propagation of the transverse damage component, D_{22} , for the bottom and top 90° plies. For this configuration, the model does a better job of capturing the observed experimental failure mode (Fig. 15). The damage is correctly concentrated in the bottom ply, which is continuously under tensile loading during each test. The prolonged stage II damage portion of the curve is due to the slow accumulation of transverse matrix cracking at fibre bundle interfaces. These cracks eventually join and propagate fully across the bottom plies resulting in a tensile matrix fracture.

Fig. 22. Predicted D_{22} damage propagation for configuration T.

Step 4: Refinement of D_{11} and D_{22} parameters using configuration X

The sixteen material parameters were identified using the first three layup configurations. The remaining two configurations, X and O30, allow for these parameters to be verified and further refined. To this end, the D_{11} and D_{22} parameters obtained from the experimental data of configurations U and T, respectively, were refined using the experimental data from configuration X, which contains both longitudinal and transverse plies. The predicted fatigue curve is compared to the experimental data in Fig. 14d. The first two stages of the fatigue curve are relatively well captured. In particular, the model captures a small drop in stiffness within the first thousand cycles. The predicted stiffness is slightly higher with an acceptable difference of approximately 4% between the stage II of the experimental curves and the model prediction. This small divergence can be explained by the likely presence of a small ply misalignments of up to 2° in the tested coupons as estimated in Sect. 3.1.1. The model however completely overshoots the failure in stage III.

Finally, Fig. 23 maps the longitudinal and transverse damage propagation, D_{11} and D_{22} , in the bottom 0° and 90° plies, respectively. As with the predicted damage propagation in configurations U and T, the damage is concentrated in the bottom plies with negligible damage occurring in the top plies. Both the D_{11}^+ and D_{22}^+ damage components evolve throughout the fatigue life albeit with a sharper increase in D_{11}^+ nearing failure, which may be due to the use of the underestimated transverse tensile strength, Y_t . Ultimately, the final failure mode observed in the experimental coupons is not at all captured. Coupons failed prematurely in interlaminar shear with no visible damage in the bottom plies (Fig. 15). The premature failure was likely caused by the presence of

$\pm 45^\circ$ stitches at the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces, which significantly weaken them. Once matrix cracking in the central 90° plies extended to these interfaces, the interlaminar failure was catastrophic.

Fig. 23. Predicted D_{11} and D_{22} damage propagation for configuration X.

Step 5: Refinement of the C_9 and $C_{i,12}$ parameters using configuration O30

The final step of the parameter identification process was to verify and check the C_9 and $C_{i,12}$ parameters associated with the in-plane shear damage component, D_{12} , using the experimental data obtained from configuration O30. As similar approach as for the treatment of the O45-configuration data was employed to extract the plastic component of the deflection, s_p , and adding it to the simulated midspan-deflection data post simulation. In the case of configuration O30, a mean value of $s_p = 0.3$ mm was recovered. The predicted deflection-cycle curve for this configuration is plotted against the experimental data in Fig. 14e.

Fig. 24. Predicted D_{12} damage propagation for configuration O30.

As with the first verification configuration, the predicted fatigue life severely overshoots the experimental data. A difference of approximately 8% is also observed between the stage II of the experimental curves and the model prediction. The latter divergence must again be due to a higher predicted stiffness compared to small ply misalignments affecting the processed laminate (Sect. 3.1.1). Indeed, implementing a ply angle offset of 1.5° towards the longitudinal coupon direction, augments the stiffness and improves the model fit over stage II of the experimental curves.

Finally, Fig. 24 maps the propagation of the in-plane shear damage, D_{12} , for the bottom and top 30° plies. The results are very similar to the damage propagation for configuration O45 (Fig. 21)

with identical damage in the bottom and top plies. Conversely, the longitudinal damage, D_{11} (not shown), is predicted to increase very little throughout the fatigue life, eventually reaching a final value of 0.084 on the tensile side. This latter result is consistent with results of configuration U, which predicts the longitudinal to be concentrated in the bottom ply under tension. Once more, the failure mode in stage III is not captured as the damage observed in failed coupons is concentrated in the bottom two plies and includes a dominant interlaminar shear component (Fig. 15).

3.3. Model validation

Of the sixteen material parameters that were identified, the parameters describing the stiffness degradation (stages I and II) are found to be suitable. However, parameters predicting the end of the fatigue curve (stage III) do not correctly capture failure as the test data used to identify is affected by the presence of significant interlaminar damage. Five coupons were tested with a final layup configuration Q (quasi-isotropic) that is more relevant for industrial structures experiencing that are designed for complex load cases. A loading fraction of 60% of σ_{f99} was selected similar to the loading fraction selected for the parameter identification tests (Table 8). Two of the five coupon tests also made use of a 3D DIC system to make strain field measurements through-the-thickness throughout the fatigue life (Sect. 2.3). The predicted fatigue curve for this configuration is plotted against the experimental curves in Fig. 14f. An acceptable correlation is observed over stages I and II with a matching of the experimental damage degradation slope. The limitation of the model lies in its inability to capture the failure mode during stage III as was the case for configurations X and O30. As a result, the model completely overshoots the experimental fatigue life.

Fig. 25. Predicted damage propagation of the three intralaminar components for configuration Q.

The predicted failure mode is illustrated in Fig. 25 by mapping the relevant intralaminar damage variables within plies. The dominant failure modes are longitudinal tensile damage, D_{11}^+ , in the bottom 0° ply and in-plane shear damage, D_{12} , in the bottom $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. Transverse tensile damage, D_{22}^+ , is also present in the bottom $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° plies albeit to a smaller extent. In practice, coupons failed suddenly in interlaminar shear at a much smaller cycle number in a manner very similar to coupons of configuration X (Fig. 15).

In turn, the through-thickness evolution of the longitudinal strain, ϵ_{xx} , determined from the DIC measurements are plotted against the predicted evolutions in Fig. 26 for the initial cycles ($N < 100$) and the cycles approaching experimental failure ($N \rightarrow N_B$). It can first be observed that the model captures the strain evolution very well and that the curves are expectedly continuous and linear. In turn, the peak strains at the surfaces increases negligibly across the majority of the fatigue life given that the damage accumulation is very slow and progressive during stage II, and that the ILS failure is sudden and catastrophic.

Fig. 26. Through-thickness evolution of the longitudinal strain, ϵ_{xx} (experimental strains are averaged lengthwise across the AOI).

It should be noted, however, that the plotted experimental curves are lengthwise averages obtained from subset rows and plotted at the average normalized height of the row relative to the AOI (Fig. 9). As such, these results smooth over strain concentrations that become visible on the coupon edges in the second half of the fatigue life. Fig. 27a maps the presence of these strain concentrations on the midspan edge surface of coupon Q-9. These strain concentrations match sectioned resin rich pockets on the coupon surface through which the NCF stitching is threaded (close-ups a-b in Fig. 12). Moreover, the largest strain concentrations appear in the fibre bundle interstices of the lower 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, which are loaded in tension.

Fig. 27. DIC results over the midspan edge surface of coupon Q-9 as $N \rightarrow N_B$: a) Lagrangian longitudinal strain field, ϵ_{xx} , through-the thickness, and b) corresponding correlation static, σ .

In turn, Fig. 27b maps the corresponding correlation statistic, σ (no relation to stress), which is a measure in pixel of the divergence between the displacement values computed between adjacent subsets. In practicality, this measure can be monitored to anticipates crack locations, where the DIC speckle pattern is breaking down due separations or rotations that exceed thresholding limits. It is difficult to estimate if the strain concentration sites, which appear to be in the process of cracking, can be correlated to the overall damage accumulation within plies. What can however be deduced is

that resin rich pockets interrupted by stitching act as damage initiation sites when loaded in tension. They may in turn be the root cause of the sudden and catastrophic ILS failures that are observed in coupons with 90° plies.

4. Conclusion

The quest for sustainable energy, whether in the European Union or worldwide, is driving innovation in lightweight composite structures spanning applications ranging from energy production to transportation. A more accurate and efficient fatigue modelling frameworks is necessary to better the design of these structures and prolong their operational life spans. This report sought to implement a state-of-the-art intralaminar fatigue damage modelling approach pioneered by van Paepegem [10] into the commercial finite element code, Simcenter Samcef.

The objective of the work was to predict the stiffness degradation and failure of a GFRP material comprised of vacuum infused, unidirectional non-crimp-fabric plies, which is currently used in the production of wind turbine blades by SIEMENS Gamesa Renewable Energy A/S, Denmark. A set of sixteen material parameters were identified, verified and refined via the development of an FE-based parameter identification tool. This tool reverse engineers the parameters by iteratively fitting the simulated fatigue curve to the experimentally determined using a sequence of five laminates with specific stacking sequences. Of note, a cycle-jump algorithm was implemented to minimize computational time. The damage state is only updated at cycle increments, over which the stiffness degradation significantly increases.

The experiments employed a four-point flexure loading configuration with 1/3-point supports. The fatigue tests were conducted in load-control using load levels based on high-fractions of the A-basis allowable flexural stress at break, which was itself obtained from a short quasi-static testing program. Previous work has relied on three-point loading configuration and based the fatigue load levels on prior tensile fatigue testing of the five layup configurations at five different load levels each. The benefit of the proposed approach is a significant reduction in test duration and number. Lastly, the populated model was validated using digital image correlation against experimental data obtained from a quasi-isotropic laminate, which is more representative of industrial composite structures in service.

The key outcome of this work is the successful implementation of the van Paepegem modelling approach and the development of a parameter identification tool fit for commercial use. However, the selected intralaminar model as implemented in FE does not on its own suitably predict the fatigue life and failure mode of the selected GRFP material. For one, the relatively complex architecture of the non-crimp fabric changed the dominant mode of failure from intralaminar to interlaminar for most layup configurations that were tested, which the model was not developed to handle. Certain layups even failed suddenly and catastrophically in delamination. In turn, the CAE model idealizes the complex mesostructure notably within plies, in which large resin pockets interrupted by stitching were observed.

As a result, the only parameters to be correctly identified correspond to the onset and evolution of intralaminar damage during stages I and II, which the model was able to reasonably predict up until the onset of significant interlaminar damage. Conversely, the values for the parameters governing failure (stage III) were identified but overshoot the observed numbers of cycles at break. A possible solution to obtain intralaminar fatigue damage for non-crimp fabrics could be to instead create and test coupons made of the same constituents, in which plies emulate the fibre density of single fibre bundles. As such, the model could be trained to predict the evolution of fatigue damage in fibre-rich regions.

On a more practical note, future work should focus on automating the parameter identification procedure with an optimization method. Some of the current modelling work had to be performed manually due to the significant albeit typical scatter in experimental fatigue results. Next, validation tests at fatigue loading levels that differ from the levels used to identify the model parameters should be conducted to verify the independence of the identified values for a given material. Lastly, both

intralaminar and interlaminar models need to be integrated into a common modelling framework with, perhaps, the addition of a static damage model. This work is the subject of UPWARDS Task 5.3.

Reference

- [1] Goal 7. *Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all*. Brussels, Belgium: European Commission. 2020. https://ec.europa.eu/sustainable-development/goal7_en, [accessed Apr 17].
- [2] Russel J. *The impact of large integrated and bonded composite structures on future military transport aircraft*. In Ch. 3, Vol. 3 of: Zweben C, Beaumont P, editors. *Comprehensive composite materials II*. 2 ed. Cambridge, UK: Elsevier; 2018. p. 92-130.
- [3] Veers PS, et al. *Trends in the design, manufacture and evaluation of wind turbine blades*. *Wind Energ* 2003;6(3):245-59.
- [4] Churchfield MJ, et al. *A numerical study of the effects of atmospheric and wake turbulence on wind turbine dynamics*. *J Turbul* 2012(13):N14.
- [5] Greenhalgh ES, Hilley M. *Fatigue failures of polymer composites*. In Ch. 5, *Failure analysis and fractography of polymer composites*. Cambridge, UK Woodhead Publishing. p. 238-78.
- [6] Sevenois R, van Paepegem W. *Fatigue damage modeling techniques for textile composites: review and comparison with unidirectional composite modeling techniques*. *Appl Mech Rev* 2015;67(2).
- [7] Van Paepegem W, Degrieck J. *A new coupled approach of residual stiffness and strength for fatigue of fibre-reinforced composites*. *Int J Fatigue* 2002;24(7):747-62.
- [8] Van Paepegem W, Degrieck J. *Tensile and compressive damage coupling for fully-reversed bending fatigue of fibre-reinforced composites*. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mats Struct* 2002;25(6):547-61.
- [9] Van Paepegem W, Degrieck J, De Baets P. *Finite element approach for modelling fatigue damage in fibre-reinforced composite materials*. *Compos Part B Eng* 2001;32(7):575-88.
- [10] Van Paepegem W. *Development and finite element implementation of a damage model for fatigue of fibre-reinforced polymers*. Ghent, Belgium: Ghent University Architectural and Engineering Press; 2002.
- [11] Carrella-Payan D, et al. *Implementation of fatigue model for unidirectional laminate based on finite element analysis: theory and practice*. *Frattura ed Integrità Strutturale* 2016;10(38):184-90.
- [12] ISO 14125 :1998. *Fibre-reinforced plastic composites — Determination of flexural properties*. Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization. 2004.
- [13] *A & B-Basis Analysis* [computer program]. Version 1.3. Riga, Latvia: Centre Composite; 2017. <http://www.composite.lv/en/site/software?id=50>, [accessed 2020 Mar 30].
- [14] *Polymer matrix composite guidelines for characterization of structural materials (MIL-HDBK-17-1F)*. Vol. 1 of: *Composite materials handbook*. Washington, DC, USA: US Department of Defense; 2002.
- [15] Epaarachchi JA, Clausen PD. *An empirical model for fatigue behavior prediction of glass fibre-reinforced plastic composites for various stress ratios and test frequencies*. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2003;34(4):313-26.
- [16] Jones C, et al. *The environmental fatigue behaviour of reinforced plastics*. *Proc R Soc A-Math Phy* 1984;396(1811):315-38.
- [17] Demers CE. *Tension–tension axial fatigue of E-glass fiber-reinforced polymeric composites: fatigue life diagram*. *Constr Build Mater* 1998;12(5):303-10.
- [18] Korkiakoski S, et al. *Influence of specimen type and reinforcement on measured tension–tension fatigue life of unidirectional GFRP laminates*. *Int J Fatigue* 2016;85:114-29.
- [19] Chang P, Mouritz A, Cox B. *Flexural properties of z-pinned laminates*. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2007;38(2):244-51.

- [20] Adam T, Horst P. *Experimental investigation of the very high cycle fatigue of GFRP [90/0] s cross-ply specimens subjected to high-frequency four-point bending*. Compos Sci Technol 2014;101:62-70.
- [21] Van Paepegem W, Degrieck J. *Experimental set-up for and numerical modelling of bending fatigue experiments on plain woven glass/epoxy composites*. Compos Struct 2001;51(1):1-8.
- [22] Curtis PT. *Fatigue*. In Ch. 11: Hodgkinson JM, editor. Mechanical testing of advanced fibre composites. Cambridge, UK: Woodhead Publishing; 2000. p. 248-68.
- [23] Sutton MA, Orteu JJ, Schreier H. *Practical considerations for accurate measurements with DIC*. In Ch. 10, Image correlation for shape, motion and deformation measurements: basic concepts, theory and applications: Springer Science & Business Media; 2009. p. 229-52.
- [24] Crammond G, Boyd S, Dulieu-Barton J. *Speckle pattern quality assessment for digital image correlation*. Opt Laser Eng 2013;51(12):1368-78.
- [25] Lionello G, Cristofolini L. *A practical approach to optimizing the preparation of speckle patterns for digital-image correlation*. Meas Sci Technol 2014;25(10):107001.
- [26] Johannes Schindelin, et al. *Fiji: An open-source platform for biological-image analysis*. Nature Methods 9, 676–682. Nat Methods 2012(9):676–82.
- [27] Potter K, et al. *Variability, fibre waviness and misalignment in the determination of the properties of composite materials and structures*. Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf 2008;39(9):1343-54.
- [28] Degrieck and J, van Paepegem W. *Fatigue damage modeling of fibre-reinforced composite materials*. Appl Mech Rev 2001;54(4):279-300.
- [29] Barnard P, Butler R, Curtis P. *Fatigue scatter of UD glass epoxy, a fact or fiction?* In Composite Structures 3: Springer; 1985. p. 69-82.